

Research Transparency: Less about Rigor and More about Responsibility¹

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Researching the governance role of sex worker rights organizations in North America has deepened my commitment to a broad conception of research transparency. Because buying or selling sex is typically criminalized, sex workers face a high risk of direct harms (e.g., violence) and indirect harms (e.g., deportation, barriers to healthcare). As such, an argument for research transparency in this case may appear misguided. Wouldn't transparency increase the risk of harms against sex workers by "outing" them to police, immigration officials, service providers, and family members? When researching individuals, groups, and communities experiencing criminalization, persecution, stigmatization, and other forms of oppression, certain kinds of transparency can indeed increase the risk of harm (Htun 2016; MacLean et al. 2018; Parkinson and Wood 2015; Shih 2015). Clearly, we have ethical obligations related to our research, which are *primary*; we have ethical obligations to protect our research participants and collaborators, and these obligations must dictate the *how* and the *what* of research transparency. In other words, our responsibilities related to research transparency are *secondary*, taking their form and substance from our primary obligations. In important ways these latter responsibilities can, and ideally should, serve in bolstering the former obligations. In this short paper, I offer thoughts on ways in which I've worked to uphold my ethical obligations and to bolster them through three broad transparency steps including (1) publishing a coding scheme, (2) archiving public transcripts, and (3) sharing a community report.

As I write this piece, I am mindful of the words of Lee Ann Fujii (2016): Research transparency "is but one scholarly value among many...and as such, cannot stand as the single barometer for 'rigor' in the discipline" (26). I want to be clear that, while I am making a case for transparency, it is not principally about a conception of scientific rigor. It is more about my understanding of my privilege as a scholar and my corresponding responsibilities and obligations to a range of individuals who are differently positioned but are involved in my research, who may read and apply it, or who are affected

by it. As a researcher, I have ethical responsibilities and obligations with respect to participants in my projects, research assistants I employ, professionals whose services I procure, members of larger research communities of which I am a part, decision makers who may draw from my research, and the public at large who funds my research (see also Maclean et al. 2018). Thus, I make judgements and corresponding decisions about the informed and active consent of research participants, fair pay and hours for my research assistants, the integrity of businesses I engage, the research materials and methodology with which I work, and the processes of communicating my work. I believe that I have corresponding responsibilities to consider the *extent to which* and the *means by which* I can achieve transparency to not only uphold but deepen the commitments articulated in the prior set of research ethics decisions. Both prior and ensuing decisions need to be contextualized and oriented toward meaningfully respecting the humanity of participants and employees, minimizing harm to them and to others who may be affected by the research, while maximizing the social good of developing and sharing knowledge.

The claims I make in this short piece are based on my long-time research with sex worker rights activist, Kerry Porth. Kerry is a prominent activist, who has spent many years advocating for legal reform to recognize and uphold the fundamental rights of sex workers. She has engaged in community organizing, given public talks and media interviews, participated in research projects, worked on the constitutional challenges to Canada's former prostitution laws, and appeared as an expert witness in parliamentary hearings on what would become the country's current laws around sex work (i.e., Bill C-36). In the following, I outline how I came to view realizing specific forms of research transparency as responsibility to communities of sex worker rights advocates, and how I have worked to fulfill this responsibility in a way that bolsters research ethics.

Research Transparency as a Responsibility

My research is a form of normative theorizing that is grounded in empirical study (see Ackerly et al. 2021).

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I often work within a critical framework but draw from both interpretivist and positivist methodologies. In recent years, my work with Kerry has become explicitly solidaristic (Johnson and Porth forthcoming). My research has taken this turn because the evidence from health sciences, social sciences, and legal analyses has become crystal clear: Criminalization increases harms to sex workers and violates their human rights (see Abel et al. 2014; see also Canada (Attorney General) v. Bedford 2013). Yet, sex workers continue to be criminalized through laws around the commercial exchange of sex. Solidaristic research involves recognizing the privilege and power we have as scholars and deploying our resources of social capital, time, and money toward ending forms of oppression. Wherever possible, I use my resources as a tenured professor to make contributions to endeavors to decriminalize (and destigmatize) sex work and sex workers.²

From the beginning, ethical and transparency considerations have been paramount in my research on sex work policy and governance. I decided to focus my analysis through an empowerment lens and examine sex workers as agents of political change, as I recognized early in my exploration of the literatures on sex work and sex workers that certain research topics had been saturated, certain communities of sex workers were over-studied, sex workers were asked to share and re-share personal information, their engagement in research projects involved personal risks and costs, much sex work research was “extractive” in nature, and some research further stigmatized sex workers. I decided to focus on the work of sex work activists and organizations to raise awareness, advocate for legal reform, and participate in policy processes. I also decided to focus first on publicly available research materials and second on research interviews. In addition, I wanted to be accountable to my participants throughout the research and beyond. This has involved checking in with interviewees regarding direct quotations and altering them if necessary, sharing drafts of my academic papers and incorporating suggested changes, paying open access fees for peer-reviewed work, and writing community reports in accessible language. Measures to fulfill my ethical obligations to research participants and collaborators have always been built into my research designs, and these measures have been bolstered by elements of transparency.

In addition to obligations to research participants, thanks to extensive conversations with Kerry, I now understand my obligations to the sex worker rights community more broadly. This community is fighting for

the decriminalization of sex work, and the fight is real. Indeed, Kerry has faced vociferous—even violent—criticism from individuals calling for the eradication of prostitution and the prohibition of sex work. Arguments put forward by “prohibitionists” are often highly moralized. Notably for this discussion, they are often based on poor research design, data, and analysis (see Benoit et al. 2019; Bruckert 2015; Weitzer 2015; Zhang 2009; see also Bedford v. Canada 2010). In many ways, the fight is for the recognition of evidence and the development of evidence-based policy. Certain steps in research transparency can enable law makers to better assess research methods, findings, and conclusions that in turn can influence their policy decisions. Kerry has always stressed to me the importance of doing sound and accessible research in order to be better than the opponents and ultimately to defeat them in the fight for policy. In a way, the transparency steps that we take represent a challenge to prohibitionists: We have nothing to hide. Do you? In a way, these steps are expressions of political solidarity with sex worker rights communities.

Another set of conversations that have deepened my understanding of research responsibilities and obligations were with Esther Shannon, a long-time feminist activist and ally to the sex worker community in Canada. In the fall of 2014, Esther shared with me her views on the recently completed parliamentary hearings on Bill C-36—a bill prompted by the successful constitutional challenge of Canada’s prostitution laws. The Supreme Court had reached a unanimous decision that the provisions in the Criminal Code concerning prostitution represented an unjustifiable infringement of sex workers’ rights to life, liberty, and security of the person (Canada (Attorney General) v. Bedford 2013). The government responded with Bill C-36, which criminalized the buying of sexual services. Esther had followed the hearings closely and observed that they were unfair with respect to the treatment by committee members of witnesses seeking the full decriminalization of sex work. “Wouldn’t it be interesting,” she asked, “to study these hearings to see if they were biased against sex worker rights advocates?” Shortly after that conversation, Kerry and I decided to conduct that very analysis.

Research Transparency in “A Question of Respect”

Our overarching question for this analysis centered on whether parliamentary committee members treated witnesses testifying on Bill C-36—*The Protection of Communities and Exploited Persons Act*—respectfully and

² The reference to being a tenured professor is deliberate. By making this reference, I wish to signal that there is a relationship between privilege and positionality, and responsibilities and obligations. The essential idea is that the “better” socially placed we are, the greater the imperatives to deploy resources toward combatting various forms of oppression, including the criminalization of sex work.

fairly. Kerry and I, along with Mary Burns, a master's student at the time, analyzed the transcripts from the hearings of the Commons and Senate committees on the bill. We focused on the questions from committee members to witnesses and found that the vast majority of them were respectful, neutral, and fair. However, our findings indicated bias from the majority Conservative Party of Canada (CPC) members with respect to witnesses against the bill, many of whom were sex worker rights advocates or allies. All disrespectful questions were asked by members of the CPC, with all but one posed to individuals testifying against the bill. CPC members asked the largest percentage of negative-tone questions, which were all directed to opposing witnesses. Similarly, all of the combative questions from CPC members were posed to opposing witnesses.

Kerry and I knew from the inception of this project that we had a responsibility to bring in elements of transparency. We decided to focus on three elements: publishing a coding scheme, archiving the hearing transcripts, and sharing a community report.³ With respect to the first element, we wanted to create and share a comprehensive coding scheme to enable individuals to understand—even scrutinize—how we conducted our analysis and developed our findings. We also wanted to provide as much information as possible to enable individuals to employ our methodology in other policy areas should they wish. The coding scheme therefore contained descriptions of our key assumptions, unit of analysis, coding process, reliability measurements, and code definitions.

We began the process of writing the scheme during our first team meeting and continued throughout the project. A foundational assumption that we wanted to clarify was that we would not be asserting truths but rather interpreting communicative exchanges. Although we would express our findings in quantitative terms, providing descriptive statistics and reliability measurements, we wanted to be clear that we would be drawing meaning from exchanges in the context of parliamentary hearings on a highly contentious topic. We thus included details about the polarized nature of positions on the legal status of sex work and about the arguments typically used by the opposing sides in this debate. Knowing that we were documenting the process for both ourselves and others, we continuously wrote research memos to ensure accuracy.

In the first coding phase, I worked face-to-face with Kerry and Mary, meeting with them several days a week. During this, we decided that our unit of analysis would be committee members' questions and that within each question, we would examine three dimensions: content, tone, and nature. The second phase involved developing evaluative codes for each dimension. We developed the codes of respect and disrespect for the content of questions. For the tone of questions, we developed positive, negative, and neutral codes. For nature, we developed the codes of sympathetic, combative, and fair. The third phase involved the consensual application of these codes to the transcripts. Our consensual coding involved weekly meetings to check our individual coding and resolve differences. Where there was disagreement over the coding of particular questions, we discussed the reasons. Once any differences were resolved, we coded the transcripts using NVivo software. Throughout the second and third phases, we refined our code definitions. In the fourth phase, close to a year and a half after we finished our consensual coding, Mary and I recoded the transcripts. Since Kerry had participated in the hearings, we decided to exclude her from this round of coding to see if there were significant differences between the two rounds. There were not. Throughout all four phases, writing and revising the coding scheme was a parallel project.

The scheme was ultimately appended to our peer-reviewed paper (Johnson, Burns, and Porth 2017a) and archived it in the Qualitative Data Repository (QDR) (Johnson, Burns, and Porth 2017b). I decided to archive it in the QDR because the administrators would issue a separate DOI for the scheme. To me, this was an important symbol of the independent value of this work but, it also meant that the work could be cited on its own. More pragmatically, it was a way of highlighting to my tenure and promotion committee the considerable work we had accomplished.

The second way we pursued transparency was by assembling and archiving the complete set of hearing transcripts. Archiving these transcripts was straightforward but time consuming. The original transcripts are housed on a Government of Canada website, searchable by bill number and date. While the transcripts remain accessible through the government's website, we believe that archiving them on QDR minimizes the labor of those wishing to examine our methodology. It takes time to navigate websites and downloading transcripts from

³ There is an extended discussion to be had about what we chose not to make transparent. Why not our memos, for example? The short response is that this would have taken more time and energy, and the methodologically relevant parts of our memos were worked into our coding scheme. Why not our interviews? Again, this would have taken more time and energy. As a basic practice, going public with transcripts requires consent not only at the beginning of an interview, but ongoing consent in terms of participants having autonomy to redact anything they may wish and to reverse their consent to public posting.

sessions on different days and during different time slots can be tedious. A DOI link now directs individuals to a single webpage that houses both our coding scheme and the transcripts.

The third component of our transparency strategy took the shape of a community report (Porth, Burns, and Johnson 2017). Kerry took the lead on the report, working to ensure that it would be legible to individuals outside of academia. She also sent out a questionnaire to her colleagues who had participated in the hearings, the results of which she incorporated into the report. This allowed Kerry to provide more context from the lived experiences of hearing participants, and enabled an airing and sharing of concerns among community members. This component of Kerry's research was very important, giving a sharp voice to serious concerns about how sex worker advocates were treated during the hearings—a voice that is too often suppressed by our academic writing. We distributed the community report through FIRST, which is an online network of hundreds of sex worker rights advocates and allies. In the work that has followed, we have continued to write community reports—including one that takes the shape of a short graphic novel (see anunusualacademic.com)—corresponding to our peer-reviewed work (Johnson and Porth forthcoming). Perhaps pushing the parameters of transparency, we believe that it is important to be creative in efforts to widely communicate our research and that creative expressions are ways of remaining accountable to the communities on which we research. I have learned over the years that sex workers and their allies are not pleased with academic norms of jargon-laden writing, the length of time between research and dissemination, and the prevalence of journal paywalls—all of which obscure research and research processes. These are hallmarks of extractive research, and I have come to understand that it is my responsibility as a scholar to counter them.

The Cost and Benefits

Developing all three components of our transparency plan involved labor. It effectively amounted to writing two more papers (i.e., the coding scheme and community report) in addition to our peer-reviewed paper. The time spent archiving the transcripts in QDR was not insignificant. The reality is that we are all maxed out—women in particular—and this additional labor contributed to an existing load. However, QDR provided very helpful administrative support, which expedited the process. In addition, there were budgetary implications of dollars per hour that Kerry and Mary worked on the project. But the costs to my research fund translated into material benefits for Kerry and Mary, who were paid between 25 and 33 Canadian dollars per hour for work

that I believe they found enjoyable.

As scholars, Kerry, Mary, and I deepened our understanding of ways of conducting interpretive and qualitative research and of how we were conducting this particular research. Working on our coding scheme and the community report created opportunities for more discussion, sharing, and learning among us. This work resulted in our spending more face-to-face time together and collaborating on a project meaningful to all of us, which resulted in deepening the basis of our friendship. As activists, we developed our understanding of sex worker rights advocates as political actors, highlighted one of the ways they participate in policy processes, and evaluated how they were treated. We did all of this in a way that enabled individuals, including skeptics and critics, to see how we conducted our work and to scrutinize it should they wish. In a small way, we signalled to prohibitionists that our research is sound and that, if they do not believe us, they can check for themselves. Maybe they will invite us to scrutinize their work in turn. Again, with respect to this particular project, we believe that this way of working is a responsibility, if not an obligation, to the sex worker rights communities.

Rigid transparency requirements by journals or funding agencies are problematic if they function as barriers to important research. As a woman of color, I am not looking for additional obstacles to getting my work published—obstacles that impact my career progress, salary and benefits, and retirement planning. As a researcher who has long been drawn to policy areas that are stigmatized (e.g., nuclear waste management (Johnson 2008) long before sex work governance), and whose area expertise is Canadian public policy, I would like to avoid additional obstacles to publishing in large international (including American) journals positioned to represent the discipline of political science. Despite these concerns, I believe that, where ethical responsibilities and obligations related to research participants, materials, processes, and implications are both upheld and deepened, and where it is feasible in terms of time, money, and other logistics, the benefits of certain forms of transparency outweigh the costs. Regularly sharing research materials with participants is a way of ensuring their active consent; communicating back to community through accessible reports can facilitate accountability; and other, more creative works can ensure that researchers are not just taking something away without giving back. In the work that Kerry and I do, transparency can be an expression of solidarity.

For scholars seeking to incorporate transparency into their work, my overarching suggestion is to think first about your ethical obligations as researchers and then about the ways in which these can be bolstered

by elements of transparency. Use your contextualized judgements about research ethics to guide your decisions about transparency. Be thoughtful; be creative. Making decisions about ethics and transparency is not easy, as Lauren Maclean (2018) and her colleagues on the QTD Working Group 1.2 render vivid (see also Johnson, Pickup, de Rooij, and Léger 2017), but it is important.

Also necessary is that those with decision-making power within the discipline examine their racialized and gendered privilege and act on corresponding obligations to conceptualize and operationalize transparency in ways that address those “ugly realities” of political science that Fujii (2016, 26) so clearly and forcefully identified.

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